

Rejuvenation From Ingrained Negativity: an AI Approach

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Negating every positivity is the mindset which leads a person into deep depression and unhappiness, if left unquestioned. The way out of the negative-statement GPT of the mental-makeup of the person, is to train it in the correct response to prompts from the environment which originally led it into negative spirals. One way of training is to associate a positive list (one element thereof) with every negative prompt that can come along.

By thus associating and practicing the link, one will gradually lead the transformer-model out of the local minimum. The transformer can then dish out local peaks, instead of troughs. The usual question is: do these peaks have any meaning? But the response is – what about the troughs? Do *they* have any meaning? It turns out that both have only probabilistic value.

So why prefer a negative statement when a probabilistically-equally valuable positive statement can be ingested instead? If this approach is adopted, then the “*manaha prasadah*” prescription of Sri Krishna in Chapter 6 of the Bhagavad Gita where he is indicating the mood with which one should initiate meditative states, becomes easy to implement. No doubt, then, that many deep meditations will fructify.